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In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

YOSHLARNING PSIXOLOGIK KASALLIKLARINI ERTA BARTARAF ETISH USULLARI

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Toshkent pediatriya tibbiyot instituti talabasi

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada bolalar va o'smirlarning ruhiy kasalliklarining oldini olishda rivojlanish epidemiologiyasining roli va ularni qo'llab-quvvatlash tizimlariga ta'siri ko'rib chiqiladi. Maqolada simptomlar paydo bo'lishidan oldin xavfga duchor bo'lishni cheklash uchun butun jamiyat darajasida ishlaydigan universal yoki birlamchi profilaktika va kasallik rivojlanish xavfi yuqori bo'lganlarni aniqlash orqali ishlaydigan ikkilamchi yoki maqsadli profilaktika o'rtasida farq bor. Unda kasallikning boshlanishi xavfi bilan bog'liq vaqtning turli jihatlari, masalan, birinchi marta duchor bo'lgan yosh, duchor bo'lish davomiyligi, birinchi alomatlar paydo bo'lgan yosh va davolanishgacha bo'lgan vaqt muhokama qilinadi. Tadqiqotda universal va maqsadli profilaktika taqqoslanadi, ularning har birini qo'llab-quvvatlash uchun zarur bo'lgan tizimlar va ularning kutilmagan oqibatlari tasvirlangan.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается роль эпидемиологии развития в профилактике психических заболеваний у детей и подростков и её значение для систем поддержки. В статье проводится различие между универсальной, или первичной, профилактикой, которая осуществляется на уровне сообщества для ограничения воздействия риска до появления симптомов, и вторичной, или целевой, профилактикой, которая направлена на выявление лиц с высоким риском развития заболевания. В статье рассматриваются различные аспекты времени начала заболевания, связанные с риском, такие как возраст первого контакта, продолжительность контакта, возраст появления первых симптомов и время до начала лечения. В исследовании сравниваются универсальная и целевая профилактика, описываются системы, необходимые для поддержки каждой из них, и их непредвиденные последствия.

Bugungi kunda jahonda epidemiologiyasi 21-asrning birinchi yarmigacha mamlakatlar va qit'alarni qamrab olgan yuqumli kasalliklar epidemiyalarining oldini olish uchun kurashdan kelib chiqqan. Yuqumli kasalliklar epidemiologiyasining vazifasi ba'zi odamlar nima uchun kasal bo'lib qolishini, boshqalari esa kasal bo'lmasligini tushuntira oladigan vaqt va makonda kasallikning shakllarini kashf etishdir. Yuqish shakllarini tushunish turg'un suvdan bezgakgacha yoki pasterizatsiya qilinmagan sutdan sil kasalligigacha bo'lgan zanjirni uzish uchun tizimli aralashuvlarni amalga oshirish imkonini beradi. Ikkinchi Jahon urushidan oldingi asr yuqumli kasalliklarga qarshi ko'plab mashhur g'alabalar davri bo'ldi.

Hozirgi vaqtda ruhiy salomatlik holati juda boshqacha. Biz hali ham asosiy xavf omillarini aniqlashga yordam beradigan "vaqt va makonda kasallikning shakllari"ni kashf etish bosqichidamiz. Umuman olganda, ko'plab yuqumli kasalliklarni yenggan "bitta zararkunanda - bitta dori" modeli ruhiy kasalliklarga mos kelmaydi (spiroxet Treponema pallidum keltirib chiqaradigan sifilis endi psixiatrik kasallik sifatida davolanmaydi). Buning natijasi shundaki, sabab omillarini aniqlash uchun vaziyatni nazorat qilish dizaynlari kabi eksperimental usullar ham kamdan-kam hollarda ishlaydi. Agar bizda sabab gipotezasi bo'lsa ham, masalan, yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloqlarni tasodifiy ravishda parvarish qiluvchi yoki parvarish qilmaydigan onalarga tayinlay olmaymiz.

Biroq, so'nggi yarim asrdagi qiyinchilik yuqumli yoki yuqumli kasalliklarni emas, balki surunkali yoki epizodik yoki yuqumsiz kasalliklarni, jumladan, ruhiy kasalliklarni qanday oldini olish edi. Yuqumli kasalliklarga kelsak, biz endi ularni keltirib chiqaradigan mikroblarni umuman bilamiz va juda oddiy ikki tomonlama hujumdan foydalanishimiz mumkin: mikroblarni yo'q qilish va ular ko'payadigan muhitni yo'q qilish. Shunday qilib, yuqumli kasalliklar uchun eski "davolash tizimlari" - vabo kasalxonalari va sil kasalxonalari - sog'liqni saqlash tizimining kichik bir qismiga kamaydi va mablag'lar deyarli butunlay ushbu kasalliklarga qarshi emlash orqali erta universal profilaktikaga sarflanadi. Birlamchi profilaktika xarajatlarining katta qismi Atrof-muhitni muhofaza qilish agentligi, maktablar va mahalliy suv xo'jaligi kengashlari kabi tibbiy bo'lmagan xizmatlar tomonidan qoplanadi.

Neyropsixologik o'yinlar va treninglar zamonaviy tibbiy psixologiyada muhim o'rin egallaydi. Ular bolaning kognitiv, emotsional va ijtimoiy rivojlanishini qo'llab-quvvatlashda, shuningdek, nevrologik kasalliklarni rehabilitatsiya qilishda samarali vosita sifatida qo'llaniladi. So'nggi yillarda neyropsixologiya sohasi nevrologiya, psixologiya, va axborot texnologiyalari integratsiyasi orqali yangi bosqichga ko'tarildi.

Neyropsixologik o'yinlar — bu miyadagi neyron aloqalarni faollashtirish, diqqat, xotira, va tafakkur jarayonlarini kuchaytirish uchun ishlab chiqilgan maxsus mashqlar tizimidir. Bunday o'yinlar o'quvchi yoki bemorning individual ehtiyojlariga moslashtirilgan bo'lib, neyrorivojlanishdagi sustlashuv yoki disbalansni kamaytirishga yordam beradi. Masalan, "Brain Gym", "CogniFit", "Lumosity" kabi dasturlar psixologik va fiziologik ko'rsatkichlarni yaxshilashga qaratilgan.

Xulosa

Bugungi kunda dunyo tibbiyot olimlari psixologik tibbiy muammolarni aniqlash hamda ularni erta davrida bartaraf etish yuzasidan ilmiy izlanishlar olib borishmoqda. Neyropsixologik o'yinlar va treninglar tibbiy psixologiyada innovatsion yondashuv sifatida nafaqat rehabilitatsiya, balki profilaktika jarayonida ham muhim o'rin egallaydi. Ular bolalarning kognitiv rivojlanishini tezlashtiradi, hissiy barqarorlikni mustahkamlaydi va ijtimoiy moslashuvchanlikni oshiradi. Shu bois, tibbiy psixologlar, pedagoglar va ota-onalar ushbu metodlarni amaliyotda keng joriy etishlari zarur. Bundan tashqari tibbiy psixologik bilimlarni boyitish bugungi

zamonning talabi bo'lib qolayotganligi butun dunyo tibbiyot psixologiyasi olimlarini yanada ko'proq izlanishga chaqiradi.

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